

LONGITUDINAL EDUCATIONAL ACHIEVEMENTS: REDUCING INEQUALITIES

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LEARN analytic framework

There is a large literature on socio-economic inequalities in the education of children and young people (CAYA). It is underpinned by a variety of theories and conceptual models. A review of reviews on socio-economic disadvantage in CAYA educational outcomes (see D2.1) has identified 66 named theories or models in 29 review articles. In D2.1, we put forward a unified conceptual perspective based on a synthesis of these perspectives. Our conceptual perspective in D2.1 has the following features. First, CAYA are nested domains of the socio-ecological environment, from those closer to the individual to those more distant. Second, individuals respond to these environments based on their functioning in different domains (e.g. physical, cognitive, emotional, motivational, social and behavioural) and their characteristics (e.g. gender, ethnicity, family socio-economic status (SES)). Third, the framework allows for the intersection of disadvantage (e.g. gender and SES). Finally, both individual age and development as well as educational stages and transitions are proposed to affect educational outcomes.

The conceptual perspective in D2.1 has informed the LEARN analytic framework (D2.2) for analysing socio-economic inequalities in education using longitudinal data (see Figure 1). Based on expert discussions with members of the LEARN consortium (held in Helsinki, Finland, on June 26, 2024), the framework has the following elements: 1) disadvantaged groups; 2) educational outcomes; 3) educational structures or school types; and 4) educational stages and transitions. It can be used for both single country case studies and harmonised comparative cross-country analyses (see LEARN Task 3.2).

Figure 1 uses **family SES** as the key dimension of educational (dis)advantage, recognising that other characteristics commonly linked in studies to social disadvantage and inequality (e.g. ethnicity/migration background) can be used instead. Family SES includes different aspects of social position, usually measured by indicators of household income, parental education and parental educational class. The LEARN analytical framework also allows for the inclusion of potential mediators in the relationship between SES and child outcomes, such as parental involvement and educational expectations for the children, the home learning environment and extracurricular activities. These are omitted from Figure 1 for simplicity.

Educational outcomes include educational achievement (e.g. exam grades, cognitive ability test scores) and completion of different educational stages (e.g. completion of upper secondary education).

School type includes the types of school differentiation that are relevant in each education system. In tracked educational systems, a key form of differentiation is academic versus vocational tracks. In school choice systems, this could refer to fee-charging versus non-fee-charging schools, religious versus state schools, or selective versus non-selective schools.

Family SES influences educational outcomes both directly and indirectly through school type.

Finally, **child characteristics** refer to ascribed or relatively enduring characteristics, such as gender, ethnicity, disability or neurodivergence. These act as potential moderators in the three pathways, i.e. the associations between family SES and educational outcomes, family SES, and school type and educational outcomes.

Using longitudinal data on the same CAYA over time, the framework allows a focus on the development of SES inequalities at different stages of the life course (e.g. sensitive developmental periods) and at key educational transitions.

Figure 1 LEARN Analytic Framework

